

Prioritizing public health and social epidemic intervention research: A protocol

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Background

The Centre for Epidemic Interventions Research at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (CEIR) has a mandate to produce high quality evidence on the effects of public health and social epidemic interventions (also known as public health and social measures; PHSM), and non-pharmacological infection control measures to fight COVID-19 and be better prepared for future pandemics (1).

During the COVID-19 pandemic several organizations and research teams developed lists, frameworks and taxonomies of interventions to control and prevent the pandemic (e.g., European Centre for Disease Control (2), World Health Organization Global Database of PHSM during COVID-19 (3) Rehfuess et al. (4)). The interventions included in these lists vary with respect to the included interventions, how they are categorised, targeted populations, settings, and timing. Furthermore, each intervention can be implemented in a myriad of ways that are not always well described.

We have very limited knowledge regarding the benefits and harms of public health and social epidemic interventions. This is particularly concerning when interventions are disruptive to individual freedoms and community functioning (5). Rigorous studies of prevention and control measures during an epidemic can provide critical evidence to inform policy and practice during outbreaks and future epidemics. Randomized controlled trials are considered the best method for assessing the benefits and harms of public health and social interventions. However, there are few examples of randomized controlled trials of the effectiveness of such interventions (6). This is especially problematic when decisions need to be made quickly regarding which interventions to implement during times of crisis: "If an encyclopedia of wrong public health decisions and poor evidence could be written for COVID-19, it must include a large share of the tens of thousands of measures taken to try to deal with the pandemic based on no evidence, weak evidence or wrong evidence" (7). It is

critical that we not only develop a comprehensive overview of all relevant public health and social epidemic interventions, but that we also develop an overview of important uncertainties regarding the effects of these interventions.

Given the range of possible interventions, and the dearth of available research, we must undertake a priority-setting process to lead future evaluations of public health and social epidemic interventions. Research priority setting has the potential to improve our efficiency in solving health problems (8). Various international organizations have developed lists of prioritized research questions (9, 10, 11). These lists have been developed using consensus methods (12), expert consultation (11). While there is currently no consensus regarding which criteria should be used to prioritize research on the benefits and harms of epidemic interventions, there appears to be general agreement that stakeholders should be involved in priority setting (8). Pre-defined criteria for prioritizing research during an epidemic allows not only for a more efficient process when determining which interventions should be evaluated, but also ensures best use of human and financial resources to evaluate the most urgent, equitable, and/or cost-effective interventions (depending on the chosen criteria) (13).

Project aim

To prioritize which public health and social epidemic interventions CEIR should evaluate.

Objectives

1. Develop a list of public health and social epidemic interventions
2. Identify important uncertainties about the effects of those interventions
3. Categorise uncertainties about the effects of interventions
4. Identify and agree on criteria for prioritizing research questions
5. Apply the criteria and prioritize questions, get feedback/input on an initial set of priorities, then finalise the priorities.'

We will address the following research questions:

1. What public health and social epidemic interventions have or could be used?
2. What are the important uncertainties about the effects of those interventions?
3. What criteria should be used to prioritize epidemic interventions for evaluation?
4. What research questions about the effects of public health and social epidemic interventions should CEIR prioritize?

Methods

This project will be divided into 5 work packages. We will use systematic review methods, consensus methods, and principles of human-centred design (14).

Objective 1. Identify public health and social epidemic interventions

We will search for relevant lists and taxonomies of public health and social epidemic interventions to control and prevent epidemics. We will include taxonomies and lists of interventions for propagated, common-source and mixed epidemics, but will be primarily concerned with interventions addressing the COVID-19 pandemic (15).

If we find a comprehensive list, we will use that as the basis for further work. If we do not find a single relevant list, we will assess the advantages and disadvantages of each taxonomy/list with support from relevant stakeholders. We will include interventions focused on general infection control and prevention measures (or standard precautions) that are always relevant, but are considered to be of increased importance during a pandemic, and infection control and prevention interventions that are relevant only during a pandemic (16, 17). We will not include pharmaceutical or biological interventions. These interventions can be targeted at individuals or larger subgroups of the population.

The resulting list of interventions will be disseminated digitally and in person to a variety of stakeholders to ascertain the completeness.

Objective 2. Identify important uncertainties about the effects of those interventions

We will use the list of interventions developed under Objective 1 to develop a framework for identifying and verifying uncertainties about the effects of those interventions. We will search the literature for lists of research questions related to PHSM to control and prevent epidemics. We will consult a stakeholder group using focus group methods and online surveys to identify important uncertainties about the effects of the interventions included in the list from Objective 1 (18). We will invite feedback from stakeholders who represent policy makers, patients, clients, caregivers, relevant academic experts, and practitioners.

Objective 3. Categorize uncertainties about the effects of interventions

Using the list of uncertainties about the effects of each identified intervention, we will categorize the uncertainties into the following four categories. We will engage stakeholders from Objective 2 to give input and feedback on this process via email.

1. Questions that can potentially be addressed outside of an epidemic **and** could be addressed in Norway
2. Questions that can potentially be addressed outside of an epidemic **and** could only be addressed in an international study or outside of Norway
3. Questions that could only be addressed during an epidemic **and** could be addressed in Norway
4. Questions that could only be addressed during an epidemic **and** could only be addressed in an international study outside of Norway

Objective 4. Identify and agree on criteria for prioritizing research questions

We will use a systematic search followed by a nominal group technique to guide the work under this objective. Nominal group techniques include brainstorming, voting, discussion and consensus (19).

Systematic search

We will search for frameworks or lists of criteria for prioritizing research questions in health. We will also contact experts in the field and conduct grey literature searches to identify relevant frameworks or lists. We will consider frameworks or lists regardless of the study designs they are intended to prioritize (e.g., qualitative, randomized controlled trials, systematic reviews). If we identify an existing systematic review of priority setting criteria, we will use this as the basis for the remaining work under Objective 4. If not, we will collate priority setting criteria from identified lists and develop a list of priority setting criteria relevant for this project.

Brainstorming

We will invite stakeholders from Objective 2 plus relevant research methodologists and stakeholders and experts with experience related to priority setting processes to a consensus process to agree on priority setting criteria.

We will conduct a stakeholder brainstorming session with a small group of researchers to consider which priority setting criteria are most relevant and/or important in the context of this project. We will use the list developed from the search above as the starting point for this discussion.

Voting

The result of the stakeholder brainstorming session will be an interim list of criteria that will be circulated digitally to relevant stakeholders and experts for feedback. Stakeholders will be asked to vote whether or not each proposed criterion should be included in the final list of priority setting criteria. We will use the outcomes of this vote to determine the final list of criteria.

Discussion

The list of criteria will be discussed among members of the stakeholder group and CEIR.

Consensus

We will present a revised list to the CEIR advisory panel and steering group with the aim of reaching consensus on the most important and relevant criteria for prioritizing research on public health and social epidemic interventions.

Objective 5. Apply the criteria and prioritize questions, get feedback/input on an initial set of priorities, then finalise the priorities.

Using the criteria developed in objective 4, we will prioritize the list of interventions identified in Objective 1. We will produce an initial set of prioritized interventions and seek feedback on this list from stakeholders involved earlier in this project, as well as any other relevant stakeholders. We will then revise the list according to the feedback.

Dissemination

The final list of prioritized research will be shared with relevant stakeholders and decision makers, published in a peer-review journal, and used to guide CEIRs research in the future.

Ethics

No ethical approval is needed to conduct this research.

Conflicts of interest

None of the authors have any financial or other conflicts of interest. All stakeholders will be asked to indicate financial or other conflicts of interest (20).

Reflexivity

The research team is made up of epidemiologists (TB, PE), health services researchers (AO, HMK) and physicians (AO, TB). The researchers will be responsible for conducting some of the research identified and prioritized as a result of this priority setting process.

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